

EXPLORATORY STUDY ON ISSUES FACED BY CUSTOMER (VIA ONLINE BUYING)

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Abstract:

Online shopping is a form of electronic commerce which allows consumers to directly buy goods or services from a seller over the Internet using a web browser. Online shopping has grown in popularity over the years, mainly because people find it convenient and easy to bargain shop from the comfort of their home or office. One of the most enticing factor about online shopping, particularly during a holiday season, is it alternates the need to wait in long lines or search from store to store for a particular item. The Internet's largest and most meaningful impact may very well be on the way consumers shop for everything from gifts, gadgets and groceries to clothing and cars. Online shopping is used as a medium for communication and electronic commerce, it is to increase or improve in value, quality and attractiveness of delivering customer benefits and better satisfaction, that is why online shopping is more convenience and day by day increasing its popularity. But many problems are facing the customer while online purchase, in this current study issue faced by the customer while buying the product through online site.

Key Words: Online Shopping and Problems.

Introduction and Methodology:

Online shopping is a form of electronic commerce which allows consumers to directly buy goods or services from a seller over the Internet using a web browser. Online shopping has grown in popularity over the years, mainly because people find it convenient and easy to bargain shop from the comfort of their home or office. One of the most enticing factor about online shopping, particularly during a holiday season, is it alternates the need to wait in long lines or search from store to store for a particular item. The Internet's largest and most meaningful impact may very well be on the way consumers shop for everything from gifts, gadgets and groceries to clothing and cars. Online shopping is used as a medium for communication and electronic commerce, it is to increase or improve in value, quality and attractiveness of delivering customer benefits and better satisfaction, that is why online shopping is more convenience and day by day increasing its popularity.

Objective of the Study:

- To study about customer facing the problems while shopping online.
- Analysing about customer agreement level of online shopping

Scope of the Study:

From this study, I was found why customers hesitate to make decision for shopping online. I analyse the various problems faced by the customers on online shopping. Find the reasons and gave the suggestions for the problems faced by the customers. Also find out the ways to overcome the problems faced by customers. Found, what are the fraud activities done on online shopping.

Methodology:

Research Design:

Research Design Research design is the detailed plan of conducting a research study. Descriptive research design has been used in the study.

Descriptive Research Design:

Descriptive Research Design Descriptive analysis attempts to explain systematically a trend, and provides data concerning attitudes and preferences towards a problem.

Sample Area:

The data has been collected from POLLACHI the city is have urban and rural area. But my study was conducted by middle of the city

Sample Technique:

Sampling technique is the choice of a subset of people from among a huge population to estimate characteristics of the 80 respondents. The focused to collection people who going to work.

Limitations of the Study:

The study has got certain limitation of which a few are listed below:

- The study is confined to selected Pollachi city only.

- The study is based upon the consumer behaviours and problems of online shopping.
- The data collected for the research is fully on primary data given by the respondents.

Tools and Techniques Used for Analysis:

- Simple percentage analysis and Chi-Square Test

Period of the Study:

The period of the study covers, from March 2022 to May 2022.

Analysis of Data:

- Data so collected was tabulated suitably for the purpose of analysis
- Appropriate statistical tool like data analysis, tabulations, and other tools were used for analysis and interpretation of data

Source of Data Collection:

Data for this study was unique in several respects. The study was based on the primary and secondary data both data were important for the analysis of consumer behaviour during online shopping. Data was collected through primary and secondary sources.

Primary Data:

Primary data is that information which is collected by researchers themselves during their own research. Primary data speaks for itself and readers automatically want to read the research matter. This information is specifically gathered for own research needs. Primary data are fresh, new and collected first time directly by the researcher himself for his research project. It was proposed to be collected by face to face questionnaires from consumers from earning people, different age and educational level to be focused on for this study.

Questionnaire Method:

Data was collected through questionnaire method. This method of data collection particularly it was being collected by working people, in this method questionnaires were collected answer met face to face.

Type of Sampling:

Random Sampling:

One of the best probability sampling techniques that helps in saving time and resources, is the simple random sampling method. It is a reliable method of obtaining information where every single member by chance. Each individual has the same probability of being chosen to be a part of a sample.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Gender:

Gender	Count	Percentage
Male	37	46.25%
Female	43	53.75%
Total	80	100%

Out of 80 Respondents under study, it is depicted that 37 (46.25%) Respondent were male while the remaining 43 (53.75%) all female, if there are more women in my study then why, Because males were 10 to 20 peoples who has been going to work peoples said they do not buy things on the Internet. So, I got a little too much for women.

Educational:

Educational	Count	Percentage
UG Degree	52	65.0%
PG Degree	18	22.5%
Others	10	12.5%
Total	80	100%

The educational segment has been divided into 3 groups –Undergraduate, Post graduates, others (Diploma, HSC, SSC, Engineering), (63.0%) most of the Respondents are from undergraduate category. (22.5%) Respondent are from Post graduate. The other category (12.5%) Respondents are Diploma, engineers and HSC, SSC educated people are more prone to online shopping for making the results more clear of my project.

Age:

Age	Count	Percentage
Less than 25	26	32.5%
26 to 40	48	60.0%
40 to 55	6	7.5%
Above 55	0	0%
Total	80	100%

Age is another demographic element that impact consumer behaviour. Online shopping products are more likely to appeal to certain age groups; younger people are more prone to online shopping as compared to others. So age groups have been divided into 4 categories, less than 25, 26 to 40, 40 to 55, above 55, the most

of the Respondents are (60.0%) 26 to 40 age group people, next less than 32.5% Respondent are 40 to 55 elders because many elders were said not Internet to buy online shopping.

Monthly Income:

Income	Count	Percentage
Less Than Rs. 20,000	18	22.5%
Rs.21,000 To Rs.30,000	28	35.0%
Rs.31,000 To Rs.40,000	13	16.25%
Rs. 41,000 To Rs. 50,000	12	15.0%
More Than Rs. 50,000	9	11.25%
Total	80	100%

Have You Felt Any Problems While Conducting Online Problem?

	Count	Percentage
Yes	71	88.75%
No	9	11.25%
Total	80	100%

Out of 80 respondents under study. (88.75%) Most of Respondent felt in the problem at online shopping. (11.25%) Respondent are not felt in the problem at online shopping.

Kind of Problem:

Kind of problem	Ranking	Count	Percentage
Delay in delivery	22*3	66	14%
Cheap quality of product	67*5	335	69%
Product damage	16*4	64	13%
Non-delivery	8*2	16	3%
Others	4*1	4	1%
Total		485	100%

Cheap Quality Product:

Majority of Respondent (69.93%) felt in the problem cheap quality of product. Facing in the online shopping.

Product Delay:

12% Respondent felt in delay in delivery.

Product Damage:

13% Respondent felt in product damage.

Non-Delivery:

3.34% Respondent felt in non-delivery.

Others:

0.85% Respondent felt in the other issues Returning problem, product changing, product colour changing, there are some problems also facing by customers. The study revealed most of the (67%) Respondents said facing biggest problem is cheap quality of products.

Level of Agreement:

Module	1	2	3	4	5	Total
A) Shopping on Internet Save Time	10	39	5	18	8	80
Percentage	12.5%	49%	6%	22.5%	10.0%	
B) Round the Clock Shopping is Major Advantage	26	50	1	2	1	80
Percentage	32.50%	62.50%	1%	3%	1%	
C) Online Shopping is Risky	10	25	2	39	4	80
Percentage	12.50%	31.25%	2.5%	48.75%	5.0%	
D) Online Shopping Will Eventually Supersede Traditional Shopping	14	36	8	20	2	80
Percentage	17.50%	45.0%	10.0%	25.0%	2.50%	
E) A Long Time is Required for the Delivery of Product and Services.	22	24	7	25	2	80
Percentage	27.5%	30%	8.75%	31.25%	2.50%	
F) Selection of Good Available on the Internet is Very Broad	12	21	5	39	3	80
Percentage	15.0%	26%	6.25%	49%	3.75%	
G) Online Shopping is as Secure as Traditional Shopping	9	13	12	42	4	80
Percentage	11%	16%	15.00%	53%	5.00%	

H) While Shopping Online I Hesitate to Give My Credit Card No	9	28	30	9	1	77
Percentage	11.7%	36%	39%	12%	1.30%	
I) Internet Reduces the Monetary Cost of Traditional Shopping	23	32	12	8	5	80
Percentage	29%	40%	15.00%	10.00%	6%	
J) Online Shopping Infrastructure in India is Under Developed	9	28	15	26	2	80
Percentage	11.250%	35.0%	18.75%	32.50%	2.50%	

Chi Square Test – Gender and Education:

Ha: There is association between gender and education

Ho: there is no association between gender and education

Observation Table:

Gender \ Education	Male	Female	Total
UG Degree	29	23	52
PG Degree	4	14	18
Others	6	4	10
total	39	41	80

Corresponding Row * Corresponding Column

Grand Total:

Gender \ Education	Male	Female
UG Degree	$52*39/80 = 25.35$	$52*41/80 = 26.65$
PG Degree	$18*39/80 = 8.77$	$18*41/80 = 9.225$
Others	$10*6/80 = 0.75$	$10*41/80 = 5.125$

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Gender \ Education	Male	Female
UG Degree	0.52	0.49
PG Degree	2.56	2.47
Others	27.56	0.24

Calculated Value = 33.875 level of significant (0.05)

Table value = 5.99

$TV \geq CV = H_0$ accepted null hypothesis

$TV \leq CV = H_a$ alternative hypothesis

This study $TV \leq CV - H_a$ alternative hypothesis accepted.

Age and Last One Year Shopping:

Last One Year \ Age	Less than 25	26 to 40	40 to 55	Total
Less Than 10	14	12	2	28
10 To 30	11	18	3	32
30 To 60	5	7	2	14
Above 60	6	0	0	6
Total	36	37	7	80

Corresponding Row * Corresponding Column

Grand Total:

Last One Year \ Age	Less Than 25	26 to 40	40 to 55
Less Than 10	$28*36/80 = 12.6$	$28*37/80 = 12.95$	$28*7/80 = 2.45$

10 To 30	32*36/80=14.4	32*37/80=14.8	32*7/80=2.8
30 To 60	14*36/80=6.3	14*37/80=6.47	14*7/80=1.22
Above 60	6*36/80=2.7	6*7/80=2.77	6*7/80=0.525

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Last One Year Age	Less Than 25	26 to 40	40 to 55
Less Than 10	0.076	0.076	0.052
10 To 30	0.642	0.6	0.014
30 To 60	0.166	0.166	0.498
Above 60	3	3	0.525

Calculate value = 8.845 Level of significant (0.05) Table value = 12.59

This study $TV \leq CV$ – H_a alternative hypothesis accepted.

Conclusion:

The study aimed to determine the problems faced by consumers during online purchase. The result showed that most of the respondents have both positive and negative experience while shopping online. There were many problems or issues that consumer’s face while using e-commerce platform. Total six factors came out from the study that limits consumers to buy from online sites like fear of bank transaction and no faith, traditional shopping more convenient than online shopping, reputation and services provided, experience, insecurity and insufficient product information and lack of trust.

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